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**PHOTO ART PROJECT
"FEMALE MULTI-COMPONENT ASSOCIATIVE IMAGE
"FERN BLOSSOM". PART 1**

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**ФОТОМИСТЕЦЬКИЙ ПРОЄКТ
«ЖІНОЧИЙ БАГАТОКОМПОНЕНТНИЙ АСОЦІАТИВНИЙ ОБРАЗ
"ЦВІТ ПАПОРОТІ"». ЧАСТИНА 1**

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**ФОТОХУДОЖЕСТВЕННЫЙ ПРОЕКТ
«ЖЕНСКИЙ МНОГОКОМПОНЕНТНЫЙ АССОЦИАТИВНЫЙ ОБРАЗ
"ЦВЕТОВ ПАПОРОТНИКА"». ЧАСТЬ 1**

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The author's idea. What the phenomenon of 'Fern blossom' is, whereas according to scientific data, the fern does not bloom and does not form inflorescences. Fern flower in the East Slavic mythology has the character of a magical plant that gives a person magical power. With the help of the fern flower, the owner of it could understand the language of animals and trees, see hidden precious treasures under the ground, heal people from various diseases, predict the future and more. It is believed that the fern blossom can be found only on Ivan Kupala night. This holiday is traditional in Ukraine and is named after the Christian Saint John the Baptist, but originates in the distant past from the pagan faith.

The presented series is named after a mysterious room which is the location of the presented shooting. We stumbled upon a huge abandoned building, during a creative search for an environment to embody the image of a girl-ballerina. The place attracted attention with its atmosphere. It made it possible to emphasize brightly the lightness, beauty and grace of the image of a ballerina-dancer, with the help of the spirit of an abandoned building. The ballerina dancer in contrast performs elements of her dance among the time-destroyed rooms and corridors. We discovered an incredible sight after having gone up to the second floor of the building and entered one of the dozen rooms. It was the whole room overgrown and covered with ferns and various plants. That seems simply impossible for the second floor. The question 'How?' hung in the air immediately. The location was chosen without any hesitation. Since it is an unbelievable rarity to witness a whole room covered with fern bushes on the second floor of the dilapidated building, we decided to connect this series of photos with just such a magical name, in honour of a rare non-existent fern flower. In some photos, the image of a girl becomes the exact rare flower that blooms only on special magical days. In such a way the flower is personified. A parallel between the image of a flower and a girl, as the embodiment of beauty, grace, a certain ideal is drawn. The series presents photos not only in the above-mentioned room but also in other locations of the abandoned building.

The image of the girl-dancer embodies the way of life that once raged within these walls, but passed into another form of revelation, revelation in nature. The aim was to illustrate two contrasts as much as possible: the decline of destruction, destruction and light, lightness, grace, beauty and elegance, which combined create a harmonious picture.

It was decided to illustrate and emphasize that among the seemingly old terrible abandoned building can also be something beautiful and vivacious. The symbol of all this is nature, which gradually takes away the building from human possessions. Such a process is illustrated with a room of ferns and fresh hydrangea flowers and the girl-dancer, who by her appearance and dance brings the energy of human existence as if reminding buildings of its past when people lived and worked there.

The stylistic solution of the model's outfit conveys lightness, beauty and tenderness, through thin fabrics of pastel colours that make up the skirt, sleeves that resemble wings, a bodysuit for dancing with pointe shoes tied with a ribbon on the legs. Much attention is paid to the accessories and details of the character. The jewellery is decorated with numerous pearls, earrings are quite voluminous in the form of shells with a pearl, that is reminiscent of the Rococo style, which means 'whimsically curved

shell'. The hair is gathered in a bundle, as ballet dancers do and the whole hairstyle is decorated with dried flowers of gypsophila. The poses of the model vary from static portraits to moving dance complexes. Some of the poses may stand out by its unnatural but flexible body curves, thus resembling the poses on the frescoes of the famous Renaissance artist Michelangelo and are called 'serpentinata', from the French word 'serpentin', from 'serpent', which means – snake.

The image of the girl-dancer itself leads to association with the ancient Greek Muses, patrons of dance, poetry and other arts.

We can draw an analogy with the ancient goddess of flowers and nature – Flora, due to the presence of flowers and nature in the photo. She is the heroine of Renaissance philosophy and mythology, often depicted in the paintings of artists in a long light dress with fresh flowers in her hands and her hair. An example is a painting of the famous Renaissance master Sandro Botticelli 'Spring'. It depicts the figure of the goddess Flora, who is scattering flowers while dancing.

In addition to some signs of the Renaissance, the image of a girl-dancer has much in common with the paintings of Impressionist ballerinas, who recreated the movement of lightness and beauty on the canvases. A striking example is the paintings of artist Edgar Degas. One of Dega's favourite topics was women, including ballerinas and dancers. He liked to depict them at a certain moment of movement or action.

Thus, the image of this photoshoot is assembled from many components depicting a ballerina who mysteriously appeared in the middle of a dilapidated building and brought life with her presence.

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Photo No. 1

**'Blossomed'
of the Photo Art Project
"Female Multi-Component
Associative Image
"Fern Flower":
Part 1**

Camera / Lens

Nikon D3S /
Nikkor AF-S 70-200 mm f/2.8G ED VR II

Settings:

35 mm | F1.41 | ISO 400 | 1/400 s

**Image No. 1 editing with
Adobe Photoshop Lightroom Classic 9:**

- Brightness and shadow areas editing
- White balance, exposure, contrast and saturation editing
- Colour correction

Light scheme

Light source:
natural light from the window.

Photo No. 2

“Life Behind the Door” of the Photo Art Project
“Female Multi-Component Associative Image “Fern Flower”: Part 1

Camera / Lens

Nikon D3S /
Nikkor AF-S 70-200 mm f/2.8G ED VR II

Settings:

35 mm | F1.41 | ISO 400 | 1/400 s

Image No. 2 editing with
Adobe Photoshop Lightroom Classic 9:

- Brightness and shadow areas editing
- White balance editing
- Colour correction

Light scheme

Light source:
natural light from the window.

Photo No. 3

**"Fern Flower. Central Composition" of the Photo Art Project
"Female Multi-Component Associative Image "Fern Flower": Part 1**

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Camera / Lens

Nikon D3S /
Nikkor AF-S 70-200 mm f/2.8G ED VR II

Settings:

35 mm | F1.41 | ISO 400 | 1/400 s

**Image No. 3 editing with Adobe
Photoshop Lightroom Classic 9:**

- Brightness and shadow areas editing
- White balance, contrast and saturation editing
- Colour correction

Light scheme

Light source:
natural light from the window.

Photo No. 4

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"The Moment of Life" of the Photo Art Project
"Female Multi-Component Associative Image "Fern Flower": Part 1

Camera / Lens

Nikon D3S /
Nikkor AF-S 70-200 mm f/2.8G ED VR II

Settings:

105 mm | F1.41 | ISO 400 | 1/350 s

**Image No. 4 editing with
Adobe Photoshop Lightroom Classic 9:**

- Brightness and shadow areas editing
- White balance, exposure editing
- Colour correction

Light scheme

Light source:
natural light from the window.

Photo No. 5

**"Renaissance" of the Photo Art Project
"Female Multi-Component Associative Image "Fern Flower": Part 1**

Camera / Lens

Nikon D3S /
Nikkor AF-S 70-200 mm f/2.8G ED VR II

Settings:

35 mm | F1.41 | ISO 400 | 1/350 s

**Image No. 5 editing with
Adobe Photoshop Lightroom Classic 9:**

- Brightness and shadow areas editing
- White balance, exposure editing
- Colour correction

Light scheme

Light source:
natural light from the window.

Photo No. 6

"A Dance with Flowers" of the Photo Art Project
"Female Multi-Component Associative Image "Fern Flower": Part 1

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Camera / Lens

Nikon D3S /
Nikkor AF-S 70-200 mm f/2.8G ED VR II

Settings:

35 mm | F1.41 | ISO 400 | 1/400 s

**Image No. 6 editing with
Adobe Photoshop Lightroom Classic 9:**

- Brightness and shadow areas editing
- White balance editing
- Colour correction

Light scheme

Light source:
natural light from the window.

Photo No. 7

**“The Blue Room. Harmony of Textures” of the Photo Art Project
“Female Multi-Component Associative Image “Fern Flower””: Part 1**

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Camera / Lens

Nikon D3S /
Nikkor AF-S 70-200 mm f/2.8G ED VR II

Settings:

105 mm | F1.41 | ISO 100 | 1/250 s

Image №7 editing with**Adobe Photoshop Lightroom Classic 9:**

- Brightness and shadow areas editing
- White balance editing
- Colour correction

Light scheme

Light source:
natural light from the window.

Photo No. 8

**"The Blue Room. Harmony of Textures" of the Photo Art Project
"Female Multi-Component Associative Image "Fern Flower"**

Camera / Lens

Nikon D3S /
Nikkor AF-S 70-200 mm f/2.8G ED VR II

Settings:

105 mm | F1.41 | ISO 400 | 1/400 c

**Image No. 8 editing with
Adobe Photoshop Lightroom Classic 9:**

- Brightness and shadow areas editing
- White balance editing
- Colour correction

Light scheme

Light source:
natural light from the window.

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